

A STUDY ON CUSTOMERS' SATISFACTION TOWARDS E-BANKING SERVICES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO IOB CUSTOMERS IN ERODE DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The services offered by a network of connected bank branches are known as core banking. Customers of the bank can use any of the participating branch locations to access their funds and do other basic activities. The current banking sector reforms, which prioritizes sustainability, efficiency, and openness, have made it more competitive for Indian banks by encouraging the creation of new foreign bank branches in India as well as the formation of new private sector banks. Customers' preferences increase as their degree of awareness rises. Customers of today demand attention and dedication; they will not settle for just politeness and care. Thus, the current need is to adopt a customer-centric strategy. Only the "Best" will survive in this competitive environment—not the oldest, nor the strongest, or the first. Thus, it is essential to use new technology to provide better service. The respondents' educational attainment has an impact on how often they use the e-banking facility. They are particularly pleased with the security, ease of access, transaction updating, and protection of confidentiality while using the e-banking services.

Keywords: reforms, sustainability, efficiency, attention, attainment, e-banking.

INTRODUCTION

In contrast to branch banking, which was the conventional method for clients to access banking services, e-banking will logically connect to or be a part of a bank's main banking system. The kinds of financial transactions that a customer can conduct through e-banking depend on the financial institutions, but typically involve checking account balances, viewing a history of recent transactions, paying bills electronically, and transferring money from one customer to another. Many banks these days exclusively operate online. The overhead costs of these "virtual banks" are lower than those of their physical counterparts. E-Banking will naturally link to or be a component of a bank's primary banking system, as opposed to branch banking, which was the traditional way for customers to obtain financial services. Depending on the financial institution, a customer's ability to do some financial operations via online banking may include checking account balances, seeing a history of recent transactions, paying bills online, and transferring funds between customers. These days, a lot of banks just conduct business online. Compared to their physical counterparts, these "virtual banks" have reduced overhead expenses.

HISTORY OF E-BANKING

The 1980s saw the emergence of the newest internet-based service delivery method, which eventually gained popularity as e-banking. Additionally, e-banking was defined as a banking method that involved accessing the banking system over the phone using a terminal, keyboard, and display. Additionally, this was also known as "Home Banking," in which clients used a numeric keypad to send instructions to the bank over a phone line in the form of tones. E-banking was first offered in New York in 1981 when Citi Bank, Chase Manhattan Bank, Chemical Bank, and Manufacturers' Hanover Bank started offering home banking services through the use of a videotex system. However, home banking was only able to become widespread in France and the UK because to the failure of the videotex system. Nottingham Building Society clients were the first in the UK to receive home internet banking services from the Bank of Scotland in 1983. The corresponding online banking service employed a BBC Micro-style computer or keyboard that was

connected to a phone and television system, and it was based on the UK's Prestel system.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In the current retail banking environment in India, with banks growing larger, branches closing, and internet banking becoming increasingly popular, the question of whether or not customers are satisfied arises, as does the nature of the fundamentals of retail banking that contribute to customer satisfaction. Industry participants may concentrate on and reinforce the critical areas that result in extremely pleased consumers by knowing the present levels of satisfaction and, specifically, the major determinants of satisfaction. Prior findings have demonstrated that the most significant in-branch elements that influence customer satisfaction in retail banking are personnel, branch location, and convenience.

One of the most important elements influencing the profitability of Indian retail banking is customer happiness. Long-term client retention is required, as it is more cost-effective than bringing in new ones (Reichheld and Kenny, 1990).

Since banking is a customer-focused sector, the focus is always on the client, and the key differentiator must be the quality of the customer service provided. Reducing expenses and boosting productivity while raising customer happiness and service quality are the challenges facing banks. Recently, focus has shifted to enhancing the quality of the customer experience during in-person interactions between bank employees and clients (Chakravarty, 1996).

The banking sector, like all other financial services sectors, is dealing with a market that is changing quickly. An unprecedented set of challenges has been presented by the introduction of new technologies, fear of economic uncertainty, intense competition, and more demanding customers, as well as by the changing climate (Lovelock, 2001).

Uday Singh Rajput (2015) investigates how satisfied clients are with online banking services and how this affects banks. This essay evaluates consumers' opinions on online banking services. The information was gathered via a

questionnaire, and percentages and ANOVA were used in a descriptive analysis. Customers using online banking services, including ATMs, home banking, and payment cards, to name a few, were found to be embracing these services. It may be inferred that around 45% of respondents see online banking favorably and are satisfied with it. The three most popular E-Banking services are bill payment, ATM access, and bank statement retrieval.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Banks introduced ATMs, mobile banking, contact centre services, telebanking, and other services one after the other in response to the changing environment. Numerous new goods and distribution methods have been launched as a result of the fast advancement of technology and the arrival of international and private banks. One of the biggest things Internet banking has done is provide consumers the convenience they so much need. The emergence of online banking presents a novel range of prospects and obstacles for financial institutions. Notwithstanding these opportunities, a number of behavioural and psychological problems, including resistance to change, faith in one's bank, apprehensions about security, a desire for human intervention, and similar challenges, hamper the expansion of online banking. In this context, an investigation on the Internet banking services offered by the banks in Erode has been conducted.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To examine awareness level of the IOB customers towards e-banking services
2. To assess the satisfaction level of the IOB customers towards e-banking services.
3. To identify the problems faced by the IOB customers towards e-banking services.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Only Indian Overseas Bank has been taken into consideration for this inquiry. Primary data were used in the investigation. The classes of professionals and businessmen, as well as employees of the government and private sector, provided the primary data. Customers of the individual banks were given a structured

questionnaire, which was created and gathered. All social classes live in Erode Town, and the researcher's hometown was a major factor in choosing the Erode District for the study. Using a suitable sample procedure, a total of two hundred respondents were chosen, with entire 200 respondents from Indian Overseas Bank. This study employed Garrett Ranking, Chi-Square, and percentage analysis as statistical methods.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study has been conducted by using primary data collected from the customers of IOB. So, personal bias may affect the results of the study.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

This section of the study analyse the data collected from the sample respondents to identify their awareness, satisfaction level and problems faced by the sample respondents.

Age and Level of Satisfaction

Age is an important factor for the purpose of decision making on matters concerned with the day-to-day life of the individuals. Age is also a symbol that the maturity of an individual. Age is one of the stages or phases in the life time, measured interm of years.

Table 1.1
Age and Level of Satisfaction

Sl.no	Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Level of Satisfaction		
				Low	Medium	High
1	Below 25	60	30	24 (29.17)	26 (23.91)	10 (26.67)
2	26-35	46	23	10 (45.83)	22 (54.35)	14 (53.33)
3	36-45	54	27	10 (20.83)	28 (15.22)	16 (13.33)
4	Above 45 Years	40	20	18 (04.17)	16 (06.52)	6 (06.67)
Total		200	100	62	92	46

Source: Primary Data

It reveals that 23/8596% of the respondents belong to the 26 years to 35 years, 30% of the respondents belong to below 25 years and 27% of the respondents belong

to 36 years to 45 years and remaining 20% of the respondents belong to the above 45 years.

Gender and Level of Satisfaction

Gender refers to the character that differentiates people as male and female based on some specific behaviour. The character and the options of the male differ from the females. Their opinion behaviour plays a vital role in using the e-banking services.

Table 1.2
Gender and Level of Satisfaction

Sl.no	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Level of Satisfaction		
				Low	Medium	High
1	Male	136	68	56 (45.83)	32 (65.22)	48 (66.67)
2	Female	64	32	32 (54.17)	12 (34.78)	20 (33.33)
Total		200	100	88	44	68

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that 68% of the respondents belong to the male category, and 32% of the respondents belong to the female category.

Marital Status and Level of Satisfaction

An attempt is made to analyse the marital status of the respondents. For this purpose the marital status have been classified under two categories viz., married and unmarried.

Table 1.3
Marital Status and Level of Satisfaction

Sl.no	Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Level of Satisfaction		
				Low	Medium	High
1	Married	70	35	18 (37.50)	36 (39.13)	16 (26.67)
2	Unmarried	130	65	30 (62.50)	56 (60.87)	44 (73.33)
Total		200	100	48	92	59

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that 65% of the respondents belong to the unmarried category, and 35% of the respondents belong to the married category.

Education and Level of Satisfaction

Educational refers to the acquiring and gaining knowledge through learning something. With the help of the education, people have such awareness to handle the cash transactions. Education also plays an important role in customer satisfaction analysis. Satisfaction level of educated people is differ from the uneducated people.

Table 1.4

Education and Level of Satisfaction

Sl.no	Educational Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Level of Satisfaction		
				Low	Medium	High
1	Higher Secondary	34	17	6 (16.67)	17 (19.57)	11 (20.00)
2	Graduate	66	33	21 (41.67)	25 (26.09)	20 (33.33)
3	Post Graduate	90	45	22 (37.50)	48 (52.17)	20 (36.67)
4	Others	10	5	2 (4.17)	2 (2.17)	6 (10.00)
Total		200	100	51	92	57

Source: Primary Data

It reveals that 45% of the respondents belong to the post graduate level, 33% of the respondents belong to the graduate level and 17% of the respondents belong to the higher secondary level and remaining 5% of the respondents belong to the others.

Occupation and Level of Satisfaction

An attempt is made to analyze the occupation of the respondents. For this purpose, the respondents have been classified under four heads viz., business / profession, employed in Government, Employed in Private and others.

Table 1.5
Occupation and Level of Satisfaction

Sl.no	Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Level of Satisfaction		
				Low	Medium	High
1	Profession / Business	60	30	15 (37.50)	25 (30.43)	20 (33.33)
2	Employed in Govt.	24	12	4 (12.50)	14 (15.22)	8 (13.33)
3	Employed in Private	66	33	22 (25.00)	24 (34.78)	20 (50.00)
4	Others	50	25	22 (25.00)	18 (19.57)	10 (3.33)
Total		200	100	48	92	59

Source: Primary Data

Inference

The table reveals that 33% of the respondents belong to employed in private, 30% of the respondents belong to business/profession and 12% of the respondents belong to employed in government and remaining 25% of the respondents belong to the others.

Annual Income and Level of Satisfaction

An attempt is made to analyse the annual income of the respondents. For this purpose, the respondents have been classified under four heads viz., less than Rs. 300000, Rs. 300001 to Rs. 5,00,000, Rs. 5,00,001 to Rs. 10,00,000 and more than Rs. 10,00,001.

Table 1.6
Annual Income and Level of Satisfaction

Sl.no	Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Level of Satisfaction		
				Low	Medium	High
1	Less than Rs. 3,00,000	36	18	12 (25.00)	18 (19.57)	6 (10.00)
2	Rs. 3,00,001 to Rs. 5,00,000	90	45	20 (41.67)	34 (36.96)	36 (60.00)
3	Rs. 5,00,001 to Rs. 10,00,000	56	28	8 (16.67)	34 (36.96)	14 (23.33)
4	Above Rs. 10,00,001	18	9	8 10	6 17	4 18
Total		200	100	48	92	59

Source: Primary Data

From the table reveals that it is referred that 18% of the respondents have annual income ranging below Rs. 3,00,000 and followed by 45% of the respondents come under the category Rs. 3,00,001 to Rs. 5,00,000, 28% of the respondents have Rs. 5,00,001 to Rs. 10,00,000 and remaining 9% of the respondents have above Rs. 10,00,001.

Family Size and Level of Satisfaction

An attempt is made to analyse the size of family members and its usage of internet banking products utilized. For this purpose, the respondents' family members have been classified under three heads viz., less than 4, 4 to 8, and more than 8 members.

Table 1.7

Family Size and Level of Satisfaction

Sl.no	Family Members	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Level of Satisfaction		
				Low	Medium	High
1	Less than 4	120	60	40 (77.08)	38 (41.30)	42 (66.10)
2	5 to 8	46	23	12 (16.67)	24 (36.96)	10 (23.33)
3	More than 8	34	17	6 (6.25)	16 (21.73)	12 (10.17)
Total		200	100	58	78	64

Source: Primary Data

Inference

From the table reveals that it is referred that 60% of the respondents have utilised internet banking services those size of the family members less than 4 members and followed by 23% of the respondents come under the category 5 to 8 and remaining 17% of the respondents family member more than eight.

Chi-Square Analysis

The satisfaction of Internet Banking Services user studied among the selected sample respondents in this study area. The opinion collected from customers are analysed with their personal factors and specific factors for the purpose of measuring their influencing over the level of satisfaction of the respondents.

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

Degree of freedom = (C-1)(R-1)

Where, O = Observed frequency

E = Expected frequency

C = Number of

Columns R =

Number of Rows

Ho: There is no significant association between attributes of the respondents and their level of satisfaction.

Table 1.7
Summary of Chi-Square Analysis

Sl.No	Attributes	χ^2 Value	d.f.	Table Value at 5% Level	Significant / Not Significant
1.	Age	10.088	6	5.348	Not Significant
2.	Gender	5.991	2	7.842	Significant
3.	Marital Status	8.256	2	7.842	Not Significant
4.	Education	4.725	6	5.348	Significant
5.	Occupation	4.671	6	5.348	Significant
6.	Annual Income	5.054	6	5.348	Significant
7.	Size of the Family	12.526	4	9.487	Not Significant

Source: Primary Data

The chi-square table reveals that there is a significant association between the gender, education, occupation and annual income and also insignificant association between the age, marital status and size of family of these attributes and the internet services used.

Garrett Ranking Technique

In the section an attempt has been made to identify the various problems encountered by the Internet Banking Services. Each problem has been analyzed separately and finally categorized by Garrett Ranking Techniques. The total and mean scores for all the factors were arranged in the descending order, Ranks given and most important problems identified and shown in Table 1.8.

Table 1.8
Problems of Internet Banking Services

Sl.No.	Statement	Total Score	Mean Score	Rank
1	Lack of Security measures	28102	140.51	1
2	Fear of online threads or scams	27895	139.48	2
3	Lack of computer literacy and internet options	26928	134.64	3
4	Difficult to operate the transactions	26630	133.15	4
5	Low Broad band internet penetration	26122	130.61	5
6	Lack awareness of banking facilities	23567	117.84	6
7	Banks ambivalent commitment levels	23195	115.98	7
8	Avoid using credit card transactions	18544	92.72	8
9	Threats from Hackers through encryption	17911	89.56	9
10	Customer mostly preferred with traditional method of operations	16725	83.63	10

Source: Calculated values

The above table shows that encountered the number of problems faced by the respondents regarding internet banking services for assigned by rank and fed the data into Garrett ranking techniques reveals lack of security measures got the first rank with 140.51 mean score and followed by fear of online threads and scams, lack of computer literacy and internet options and vice versa.

FINDINGS

1. 30% of the respondents belong to the below 25Years are highly satisfied the internet services.
2. 66.67% of the respondents belong to the male category are highly satisfied.
3. 73.33% of the respondents highly satisfied belong to the unmarried category.
4. 36.67% of the respondents belong to the post graduate level of the education respondents highly satisfied.
5. 50% of the respondents satisfied the internet services belong to employed in private sector.
6. 60% of the respondents have annual income ranging below Rs. 3,00,000 are highly satisfied the internet banking services.
7. Out of 200 respondents, 66.10% of the respondent's levels of satisfaction are satisfied with doesn't aware of the internet banking products advertisement.
8. The chi-square table shows that there is an insignificant correlation between the age, marital status, size of family, and education level of these characteristics and the internet services utilized, but a strong correlation between gender, education, employment, and yearly income. According to the Garret ranking techniques, a key issue with internet banking services is the absence of security precautions. Other issues include fear of online dangers and frauds, a lack of computer proficiency, limited internet possibilities, etc.

SUGGESTIONS

1. Awareness level about internet banking is very less among customers. So banks have to conduct customer meet regularly to educate the customers on internet banking. The bank can also distribute booklets contains information about the new schemes and it can be distributed directly to the customers.
2. Introduction of core banking should be speeded up because size of the bank is considered an important factor in choosing internet banking.
3. Organization structure has to be changed to accommodate IT experts to give training in computer to the employees.

4. The call center concept has to be brought down to the STD booth level in this aspects an ordinary persons may have to utilized the internet banking services..
5. Banks can also extend more loan facility to buy computers which in turn will increase the internet usage level among the customers of our banks.
6. An exclusive TV channel or programme for public sector banks can be opened to educate customers in regarding internet services and their utilization.
7. The banker is expected to serve the customers without any delay for quarries and itis advisable to follow time management principles consistently.

CONCLUSION

Customers' preferences increase as their degree of awareness rises. Customers of today demand attention and dedication; they will not settle for just politeness and care. Thus, the current need is to adopt a customer-centric strategy. Only the "Best" will survive in this competitive environment—not the oldest, nor the strongest, or the first. Thus, it is essential to use new technology to provide better service. The respondents' educational attainment has an impact on how often they use the online banking facility. They are particularly pleased with the security, ease of access, transaction updating, and protection of confidentiality while using the online banking services. The popularity of online banking.

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